

Facets of S_n

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Previous articles **[1]** – **[6]** have detailed some features of lower-order symmetric groups, obtained often after extensive computational effort. Here, more general observations are collected for reference.

Elements of the symmetric group S_n may be described in several equivalent ways:

F1) Digit strings of distinct integers k_j from 1 to n , in decimal format $k_1k_2k_3\dots k_n$

F2) $n \times n$ matrices where every row has exactly one '1', in distinct columns

F3) Cumulative column counter digit strings: $k_1(n+k_2)(2n+k_3)\dots((k-1)n+k_n)$

The image below shows these options for the S_6 element 351462

$$[3\ 5\ 1\ 4\ 6\ 2] \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} [3\ 11\ 13\ 22\ 30\ 32]$$

Properties of S_n ($n \geq 2$) include:

P1) The group has $n!$ elements

P2) The individual digit sum of any element in F1) is $n(n+1)/2$

P3) The individual digit sum of any element in F3) is $n^2(n-1)/2$

P4) For any integers $1 \leq q < p \leq n!$, $S_n(p) \equiv S_n(q) \pmod{9}$

P5) S_n serves as a source for S_{n+1} ; informally $1 + S_n \Rightarrow S_{n+1}$

The congruence P4) is not as mysterious as it seems.

Let

$$S_n(p) = k_1k_2k_3\dots k_n$$

$$S_n(q) = t_1t_2t_3\dots t_n$$

be two elements in S_n ; the k_j 's and t_j 's are distinct integers from 1 to n within each element, all values taken, though exactly once. In decimal notation then

$$S_n(p) = 10^{n-1}k_1 + 10^{n-2}k_2 + 10^{n-3}k_3 + \dots + k_n$$

$$S_n(q) = 10^{n-1}t_1 + 10^{n-2}t_2 + 10^{n-3}t_3 + \dots + t_n$$

Now, each element in S_n is made up of the same constituent integers; the variations are in the powers-of-ten scale factors. In subtraction, alignments of identical integer entries will then lead to differences in powers-of-ten; for non-negative exponents $i \geq j$, these difference possibilities are (ignoring signs)

$$10^j(10^{i-j} - 1)$$

and the (non-zero) terms in parenthesis can be any one of 9, 99, 999, These integers obviously have 9 as a multiple, which can in turn be factored out of the overall subtraction; hence the ensuing congruence.

Finally, the images below show the path-of-ones for three S_6 elements.

Path length for each of the 720 elements is plotted next; minima occur for 123456 and 654321

References

- [1] A. Cusmariu, 'Spawning S_4 from Kronecker products', [10.5281/zenodo.10452480](https://zenodo.org/record/10452480)
- [2] A. Cusmariu, 'S4 once over easy', [10.5281/zenodo.10613871](https://zenodo.org/record/10613871)
- [3] A. Cusmariu, 'S5: piece of cake, almost', [10.5281/zenodo.10630734](https://zenodo.org/record/10630734)
- [4] A. Cusmariu, 'S6: The whole enchilada and more', [10.5281/zenodo.10654847](https://zenodo.org/record/10654847)
- [5] A. Cusmariu, 'S6 again: Circulant evolution at work', [10.5281/zenodo.10687840](https://zenodo.org/record/10687840)
- [6] A. Cusmariu, 'Bootstrapping from S_n to S_{n+1} ', [10.5281/zenodo.10693922](https://zenodo.org/record/10693922)